

<https://www.abrj.org/>

Impact Factor 2.30

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

News Frames Emotion: Analysing How Audience are Influenced by News Frames

Author Details:

Akpoghiran, Idamah Patrick

Department of Mass Communication, Western Delta University

Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria Email: pidamah@gmail.com

Tel No: +2340837794099

Abstract:

As a persistent pattern of selection, interpretation, emphasis and presentation, news frames is very fundamental in influencing individual emotions. News is the construct and presentation of the news media. The study examines how audience emotions are influenced by news frames. The study is anchored on the theory of media framing, which deals with how the media package and present information to the audience or how audiences feel about an issue. Using analytical review of literature, the paper is exploratory and explanatory in nature as it adopts the gathering of relevant literature data with the sole aim of interpreting these data in order to achieve the desired aim of the study. Arising from the analyses of data, the study submits that individual's perception and reaction to news is a product of the journalistic news frame. This is because news frames involves selecting and emphasizing words, expressions, and images and these are capable of influencing audience's cognitive, attitude and emotional effects. However, audience emotions to news largely depend on the state of the audience's selection, interpretation and perception processes of the news. Framing is a selective construct with effect.

Keywords: Audience; Emotion; Influence; News frames

1. INTRODUCTION

Studies on news framing are complex because of the different dimensions involved in the concept. Framing has been considered as one of the most popular areas of news research (Valenzuela, Piña, & Ramírez, 2017), as such, many of the studies on news framing have been on framing effects (eg. Nabi, 2003; Lecheler & de Vreese, 2013; Schuck, & Feinholdt, 2015; Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019). Earlier studies were on framing theory (Gregory Bateson in 1972, Goffman in 1974, cited in Dorfman & Krasnow, 2013; Entman, 1993; Pan, & Kosicki, 1993; de Vreese, 2005). Studies have also concentrated on determining the cognitive and attitudinal effects of news frames (de Vreese, 2011; Igartua; Moral-Toranzo; & Fernández; 2011). For example, de Vreese et al. (2011) point out that “framing can help us to understand how citizens make sense of political, social, and economic issues” (p. 180). Gross and Brewer (2007) had a study on how news frames can influence what citizens feel about politics. The study showed how news frames make the electorates to decide their choice and make opinion about political candidate for election. In another way, news frame explained how audience makes sense from news story.

Studies on news framing were hinged on multiple areas of emotional effects (eg. Nabi, 2002; Pantti, 2010; Kim & Cameron, 2011; Wahl-Jorgensen, 2016; Beckett, & Deuze, 2016; Lecheler, 2020 etc.). For instance, Lecheler and De Vreese (2019) did a study on news frame effects. Their study showed that news framing effect depends on how a frame corresponds to knowledge constructs that are both available and accessible in a person's mind. To them, a news frame can affect an individual by stressing certain aspects of

reality and pushing others into the background: This is due to the selective function of news frame. Conceptually, the authors defined news frames as a central organizing idea or story line that provides meaning to an unfolding strip of events, weaving a connection among them.

Studies also exist to show the processes of news framing effect or influence (Slothuus, 2008; Nabi & Oliver, 2009; de Vreese & Lecheler, 2012). For example, De Vreese and Lecheler (2012) research focused on three different processes that can mediate framing effects. These were accessibility change; belief importance change; and belief content change. The focal points in these three factors were beliefs and changes. Basically, belief is a prime factor of change. Belief brings about changes. People work on news depending on how it is framed. News therefore brings about change. Otieno; Spade; and Renki (2013) were of the opinion that framing draws attention to relevant aspects of information while detracting it away from other equally relevant aspects.

Also, the roles of news knowledge by the individual audience, frame strength and source credibility have been researched as moderating factors on framing effects (e.g., Druckman, 2001a; Lecheler, de Vreese, & Slothuus, 2009). These factors and other salient issues were believed to be moderating factors on framing.

However, how news audience is influenced by news frame remains inadequately researched among communication scholars in Nigeria. There are perhaps inadequate studies on news frame in Nigeria. Perhaps, communication scholars in Nigeria have not adequately looked into this all-important subject of how news influences audience's emotions.

Objective and Methodology

The mass media are playing persuasive roles in influencing audience perceptions and emotions through the presentation of news or news framing. As a result of audience exposure to the media on daily basis (Beckett, 2008; 2010), people's lives are correspondingly lived in with the media (Beckett, & Deuze, 2016), whereby audience emotions are likely associated with media framing.

Objective: The broader aims of the study are to discuss variables that determine news framing; processes and factors that influence news frames; types of news framing. Specifically, the aim of the study among others is to analyse how news frames influenced audience.

The paper is exploratory and explanatory in nature as it adopts the gathering of relevant literature data with the sole aim of interpreting these data in order to achieve the desired aim of the study.

2. BASIC CONCEPTS REVIEWED

a. Frame and News Framing

There are streams of studies on the definition of frames. For instance, Gamson and Modigliani (1989) defined a frame as "a central organizing idea or story line that provides meaning to an unfolding strip of events" (p. 143). Frame had been seen as what an issue is about, that is, how one should make sense of it (Schuck & Feinholdt, 2015). As far as back in 1974, Erving Goffman sees frames as are useful devices for human beings to make sense of the world in all kinds of everyday situations. For him, frames are culturally bound and serve to reduce the complexity of our everyday world. Framing has been defined as "a process through which a communication source defines and constructs a public issue or controversy and can have significant consequences for how people view and understand an issue" (Schmitz; Filippone; & Edelman, 2003, p. 386).

In its most basic sense, a frame is a construct. News is the construct of the media. As Lecheler, Schuck, and de Vreese (2013) noted, framing implies that news content is constructed through particular features that provide clues about the interpretation of the text and the news event itself, suggesting certain attributes, judgments, and decisions. This suggests that news is the presentation of the news media. News is as the media present it. This is done through the use of selection, salience or emphasis, exclusion and/or elaboration (see, e.g., Chong & Druckman, 2007). Selection and emphasis on a particular story also explained news frame. Importantly, a news frame represents a consistent construction of an issue, suggesting certain associations,

attributes, judgments, or decisions. Simply put, it is more than just an isolated argument on a particular issue. News framing in another sense refers to the observation that the media present on the same issue in very different ways, emphasizing certain aspects (Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019).

b. Criteria for Framing: Variables that Determine News Framing

To recognize and identify that framing exist in news, studies have suggested certain criteria or devices. Cappella and Jamieson (1997) suggested four criteria that a frame must meet. First, a news frame must have **identifiable conceptual and linguistic characteristics**. Second, it should be **commonly observed in journalistic practice**. Third, it must be possible to **reliably distinguish the frame from other frames**. Fourth, a frame must have **representational news framing effects theory validity** (i.e., be recognized by others). For Entman (1993: 52), frames in the news can be examined and identified by “the presence or absence of certain keywords, stock phrases, stereotyped images, sources of information and sentences that provide thematically reinforcing clusters of facts or judgments”. Gamson and Modigliani (1987) identify these criteria as “framing devices” that condense information and offer a “media package” of an issue. They identify the use of (1) metaphors, (2) exemplars, (3) catch- phrases, (4) depictions, and (5) visual images as framing devices. Lecheler and de Vreese (2013) identified repetitive exposure to the same frame or to competing frames and/or repeated exposure with different time delays (when news is repeated in several minutes or hours to weeks) to track the strength and persistence of framing effects over time and in a more realistic setting.

It can be taken that a frame is identified in a news by the framing or casting of the headline; the use of diction in the body of the story; the duration of the coverage; the frequency of the news coverage on that particular story (this means developing story); and the manner the news was presented by the reporter (the manner of presentation includes extent of interest given to the news, repetition of the same story along with videos, and the numbers of reporters used on the same story, and the various experts invited to talk about the story.

Given these factors mentioned above, and the definition that that media frames is the persistent patterns of cognition, interpretation, and presentation, of selection, emphasis, and exclusion, by which symbol handlers routinely organize discourse, whether verbal or visual (Gitlin, 1980), individual becomes influenced and react to the manner in which news is framed. To Vliegthart and Roggeband (2007), for a news material to be classified as framing, it must (1) dominate the news for a more extended period or permanently change the political power base in society. (2) be incongruent with how the issue has been framed before the event or result in political actors propagating other frames gaining dominance in society. However, circumstances can change the way the media can frame a group, nations, or individuals (Makata, 2021). These lines of studies explained that framing is a selective construct with effect.

In line with the above items or criteria for identifying news framing, Pan and Kosicki (1993) identified four structural dimensions of news frames. These were: (a) syntactical, (b) script, (c) thematic, and (d) rhetorical structures. Syntactical structures are: headline, lead, episodes, background, and closure. Script structure provides a description of events and activities in a consistent and stable way. Thematic structures in a story consist of a main theme, subthemes, and supporting elements. Rhetorical structure is related to journalists’ writing style, involving five framing devices such as metaphors, exemplars, catchphrases, depictions, and visual images. These structures are parts of journalist induce emotions or news framing.

The way information is presented via news elements can influence the way people perceive the issue (Kim, & Cameron, 2011). By this, the media not only set agenda for public discussion but news becomes ‘framing’. The agenda setting and media framing postulations are applicable to this study. De Vreese (2005) identifies two types of frames (not types of effect) in media content: **generic frames and issue-specific frames**. Issue-specific frames are bound to a particular issue or issues based that have great human interest of national concerns, such as conflicts, political issues, financial or economic consequences, health issues and others that greatly affect human interest. Generic frames are variety of issues that are commonly applied to a wide range of topics reported in the media.

All these criteria or variables of identifying news frames imply that news frame is the selective construct of the news media, and for the purpose of attention-getting or 'stay on the news' as CNN calls it. Framing therefore has to do with effect.

c. News Framing Effects

Framing effects refer to the process in which how people see specific issues, make interpretations and, how it affects them. Different scholars have researched and classified news framing effects from different types. News framing is an extension of news effect studies in the mass media. Scholars have identified types of or processes of news framing effects

By thinking about an issue in the news and discussing it, news framing effect occurs as **Issue interpretations**. When news issues are identified and discussed by way of pondering about it, analyzing and interpreting it, it becomes effect. The news induces audience into discussion. Price et al. (1997) suggested that by activating some ideas and values, news can encourage particular trains of thought. Another news framing effect is **cognitive effects**. Cognitive effect of news frames is the ability to affect learning. News affects cognitive development. A news issue that is identified, discussed, interpreted and recalled, is learned news. This is why Lecheler and De Vreese, (2019) claimed that learning from the news is a core interest in media-effects research. Cognitive development in news frame occur when a news or issues is consistency repeated as developing story. What the news media present to us as news become knowledge to us. The media environment is so monopolized by television for example, that its issues or news are continually learned and relearned. This view stresses the cultivation theory by Gerber and Gross in 1976 to the relations of emotions. Gerber and Gross (1976) believe that television for example, is responsible for a major 'cultivating' and 'acculturating' process according to which people are exposed systematically to a selective view of society on almost every aspect of life, a view which tends to shape their beliefs and value accordingly.

Another process of news effects is **attitudinal effect**. When news frame (based on the extent of framing) is interpreted by the news audience whereby giving it a meaning, it leads to changes in opinions. Attitude is guided by thoughts and depositions that are recalled. Emotional or affective effect is one of the core aspects of news framing effect. Studies are more concerned about news frames on audience emotions. Emotion is a fundamental psychological aspect of humans, which cannot be ruled out from journalism neither from the journalist or the receiving end—the audience. Kim and Cameron (2011) revealed that emotional news frames (anger-inducing or sadness-inducing) affect people's emotional response. To them, emotional news frame affect how individuals perceived news and react to the news report. For example, news frame on the heat of the COVID 19 pandemic which could be regarded as panic reporting by the news media (Akpoghiran, 2022) plunged the public into anxiety and panic (Dong & Zheng, 2020).

News frames on electoral participation could lead to higher electoral turnout or low turnout. News frames for example on politicians' behaviour could determine audience perception and thus, behaviour of politicians. All these types of news frames point to **human-interest frame**, which emotionalizes and dramatizes information and often accentuates individual affectedness (Otieno; Spade; & Renki, 2013). That is, the human-interest news value often translates into a story about an event that is centered on a specific individual.

The **Equivalence framing** as a type of news frames effect was postulated by Scheufele and Iyengar (2012). The equivalence framing directs attention to different aspects in a factually identical description. It presents factually equivalent information from different perspectives. Also, there is the **Emphasis framing** by Entman (1993) and Tankard (2001), which suggests a certain perspective by emphasizing specific, equally true, yet different subsets of aspects of a topic without the assumption that the information presented is necessarily factually equivalent. Emphasis frames present information that suggests a certain perspective, yet is not necessarily factually equivalent between different frames. Emphasis framing is common in public media and is therefore often found in research on media effects and specifically news frames (Otieno; Spade; & Renki, 2013).

d. News framing Process

It is important to stress that news framing is a process, and there are certain factors that influence the process of a frame. These factors determine how individual perceived and react to news. Lecheler and De Vreese (2019) identify the dynamic processes of news framing to involve **frame building** (how frames emerge); **the presence and development of frames in the media**; and **frame setting** (the interplay between frames and citizens). Entman (1993) noted that frames have several locations: 1. the communicator, 2. the text, 3. the receiver, and the 4. surrounding culture. These locations emphasize framing as a process that consists of distinct stages namely: 1. frame building, 2. frame setting, and 3. individual- and societal- level 4. consequences of framing (D'Angelo, 2002; de Vreese, 2005; Hänggli, 2012).

On framing building and framing setting, from the views of Lecheler and De Vreese (2019), it refers to the process of competition, selection, and modification of frames from elites or strategic communicators by the media. This process is influenced by forces that are internal to the newsroom and news organizations, as well as by external forces such as political elites, social movements, and interest groups. The influence of these external forces is apparent, for example, when journalists use parts of political speeches to illustrate an issue. The influence of internal forces is visible in the structure and emphasis of a news story.

On framing setting, the authors refer it to mean the interaction between news frames and individuals' prior knowledge and predispositions. Frames in the news may affect learning, interpretation, evaluation of issues and events, and so on. On the societal level, frames may contribute to shaping social-level processes, such as political socialization, decision- making, and collective actions.

Invariably, the processes of framing are guided and influenced by both internal and external forces. De Vreese (2005) distinguishes between factors that are internal to the news production process and those that are external, with both affecting the frame building process. **Internal factors** are **editorial policies, the reporter and the editor perceptions of news frame, and news values**, which shape the day- to- day work of journalists. For example, the news value of focusing on domestic consequences can translate into a journalist framing a story about an international event in terms of domestic economic ramifications. **External factors** are influences from stakeholders like **elites, interest groups, civil society organisations, and social movements**. The points held by De Vreese (2005) on internal and external forces imply **journalistic news frame**. Journalistic news frames play a transformative role. Journalistic news frames implies the process where a journalist and the news media organizations shape their selected topics in their own particular manner and style. Brüggemann (2014) defines journalists' frames as 'cognitive patterns of individual journalists', while Scheufele (2004) sees it as 'consistent patterns of expectations' and a 'consistent bundle of schemata'. To Nelson and Willey (2001), a journalist frame is an issue-specific position based on values or belief systems. Journalists' frames are thus part of the internal factors of news framing effects that affect the frame-building process and in some cases can lead to actual journalistic news frames in the coverage (Lecheler & De Vreese, 2019).

Further to the above, journalistic news frames effects have been identified by other studies (Neuman, Just, & Crigler, 1992; De Vreese, 2012). These effects are conflict frame, attribution of responsibility frame, morality frame, economic consequences frame, and human-interest frame. For instance, responsibility frames emphasize the responsibility of an individual or a group for a certain event or outcome, while the morality frame presents an issue in the context of religious or ethical perspectives. The economic consequences frame focuses on economic consequences for individuals or groups. The human-interest frames use specific features, such as dramatizing or emotionalizing vocabulary to catch the audience's attention and often lend the story an individual, personalized touch (Semetko & Valkenburg, 2000). These different journalistic news frames are known to exert differential emotional responses (Gross, 2008). The points held by some scholars on the factors that influence individual's perception and reaction to news frames could be described as 'audience-emotion effect', which explains that news frames affect audience emotions (Kim, & Cameron, 2011; Zhang, 2015; Lecheler, 2020). It explains that individual's perception and reaction to news is a product of the journalist.

e. News frames and Audience Emotions

Emotion in this study is taken as reaction like anger, shock, fear, worries, and the positive side, joy, peace, calmness, and indifferent to news. Audience perceptions and reaction to news is a process of media

framing. Media framing looks at all the angles of the news presented, time of the news, and the degree of discussion given to the news, salient areas invoked, and the prominence given to the news. That news frame makes the media to dictate to the public how to think about certain matters (e.g., de Vreese, Boomgaarden, & Semetko, 2011; Scheufele & Tewksbury, 2007), the concept of the news frame is particularly relevant to audience processing of news (Igartua; Moral-Toranzo; & Fernández; 2011). For example, De Vreese et al. (2011) noted that framing can help to understand how citizens make sense of political, social, and economic issues. As Igartua; Moral-Toranzo; and Fernández (2011) pointed out that frames exert an influence upon what people think for example, about political and other social issues. To Gross and D'Ambrosio (2004), frames may influence not only opinion but also the emotional responses that people report. That news frames present to us something to think or ponder about, it therefore influences our cognitive and emotions. That news frames involves selecting and emphasizing words; and images captured (Scheufele, 1999, 2000), it is capable of influencing audience's emotions.

Since framing is concerned with the presentation of information, and that the media play a key role in forming opinions by influencing people's understanding and perception of a topic (Otieno; Spade; & Renki, 2013), emotions become dependable on news presentation or framing. This corresponds with the study by López and Sabucedo (2007) that framing effects found influences of news frames on opinion formation. However, several authors have showed that news frames emotions are moderated by factors such as the recipients' issue involvement, perceived importance (Petty, Cacioppo, Schumann, 1983; Lecheler, de Vreese, Slothuus, 2009); and prior knowledge (Van Gorp, Vettehen, Beentjes, 2009; Igartua, Moral-Toranzo, Fernández, 2011).

Different news frames can promote different emotions. For instance, in a study, Nabi (2002) found that different versions of news stories on domestic terrorism elicited expected emotions of anger, and fear. Recurrent terrorists attacked in some parts of Nigeria, is capable of arousing fear and panic among news audience. Nabi (2003) refers to this notion as "the emotion-as-frame perspective" (p. 230), meaning that "discrete, context-relevant emotions selectively affect information processing, recall, and judgment" (p. 228). Nabi also noted that "repeated pairing of certain emotions with particular ideas or events shapes the way in which one interprets and responds to those events" (p. 227). This implies that consistent emphasis on a particular news story and framing shapes audience's emotions.

News frame is news emphasis. For instance, on the 28th March, 2022, an Abuja-Kaduna train was attacked in Ktari, Kaduna, Nigeria by gun men using explosive device, killing some persons while a large number of the passengers were kidnapped by the gun men. The news coverage for weeks emphasizes on poor security systems in the country, and the fate of the kidnapped victims. At the instance of the event, anger dominated people's first response and fear to use the train to travel in that route. Repeated emphasis on the news caused panic on matters of security in the country. News frame leads to audience selection, interpretation and acceptability of the news. Audience emotions on news presentation stemmed from news frames, a process from the reporter and editor selection, perception and interpretation of the news story.

3. THEORETICAL SUPPORT

The study is anchored on Media Framing Theory. The concept of framing was posited by Gregory Bateson in 1972 (Arowolo, 2017) and later by Goffman in 1974, as 'Frame Analysis' (Dorfman, & Krasnow, 2014). According to Arowolo (2017), framing describes the practice of thinking about news items and story content within familiar context. Because the notion of framing has been increasingly central to media analysis (Shih, Wijaya, & Brossard, 2008), it deals with how the media package and present information to the audience or how audiences feel about an issue (Gamson & Modigliani, 1989). The basis of framing theory is that the media focuses attention on certain events and then places them within a field of meaning. According to Dorfman and Krasnow (2014), framing is the process of reconciling new information with one's existing understanding. Journalists in media framing decide which facts, values and perspectives will be given prominence. This means

that reporters certainly apply their own perspectives and interpretative frames when packaging news. Media framing is journalist narratives.

The fundamental assumptions of media framing theory hold that media framing draws audience attention to certain attributes of the objects or issues of the news coverage, and it also helps individuals interpret data so that their experiences can be understood in a wider social context. Audience emotions are affected by their perceptions. Perception is the idea or image we create about something and the meaning we make from it. To Perreault and McCarthy (2005), perception is how we gather and interpret information from the world around us. Hawkins, Best and Coney (2004) described perception as exposure, attention and interpretation. Since we constantly gather and interpret information from our environment, it is accurate to say therefore that perception is a process and not an action (Amodu, 2006). Démuth (2013) says perception is a process of acquiring and processing of information through the sensory. Therefore, perception seems to be the centre of news frames to audience emotions. Scott and Brydon (1997) highlight factors that can influence perception in a communication process. These are: **background:** The way an individual interprets a message depends on his background, and past experiences as well as circumstances that surround his life, and his mood as at the time of receiving the news. Another is **intensity:** This refers to how prominent the message is. Important news attracts attention. Also is **extensity:** This involves the attention drawing effect of the message. The extensity of the news could have great or small effect on the audience. There is **concreteness:** This refers to a message that is not ambiguous. It must be clear for the audience to understanding. Interpretation (perception) is made from a clear and simple story. **Contrast and Velocity:** This refers to the degree to which the communication messages and people appear striking, moody, and novel. **Impressivity:** This refers to the combination of all the above mentioned factors. These factors help the audience to make meaning out of the news received.

Framing is an expansion of the agenda-setting postulation by focusing on the essence of the issues at hand rather than on a particular topic as both examined what information is gathered, interpreted, and how it is combined to form a causal judgment (Fiske & Taylor, 1991; Shrum, 2017). Shih, Wijaya and Brossard (2008) believed that media framing have implications on attitude. Gamson and Modigliani (1989) noted that media framing is media package and presentation of information to the audience or how audiences feel about an issue.

In the light of this study, media framing as a key component of audience emotions deals with the process by which people extract meaning from media contents. The key words here are persistent, selection, interpretation, presentation, and emphasis on news; which basically determine the state of audience emotions. As it were, news frames on the COVID 19 pandemics or Russia invasion of Ukraine, for instance, when continuously reported on television with horrifying images as developing story, may cause physical functional disorders, depression and hypertension (Batelaan; Seldenrijk; Bot, Balkom; & Penninx 2016; Liu; Li NA, Li WA; Khan, 2017). Media framing is therefore, the way or manner news is presented.

How Audience are Influenced by News Frame

Fig. 1: Structural Processes of News Frames

News Frame Structures	Structural Processes
Syntactical	Syntactical structures are the “headline, lead, episodes, background, and closure (Pan & Kosicki, 1993). By the framing of the headline, for example, when insecurity or public health risk reports like the COVID 19 are consistently presented as the first main news items on TV or boldly framed in the front page of a newspaper. The systematic and grammatical orderly arrangement of the story may raise emotion or reaction to the story.
Script	Script structure provides a description of events and activities in a consistent and stable way (Pan & Kosicki, 1993) that is capable of determining audience views. This also includes the body of the news and the duration of the coverage.
Thematic	Thematic structures in a story consist of a main theme, subthemes, and supporting elements (Pan & Kosicki, 1993). A video story is a convincing supporting element.

Rhetorical	Rhetorical structure is related to journalists’ writing style, involving five framing devices such as metaphors, exemplars, catchphrases, depictions, and visual images (Pan & Kosicki, 1993). Grammatical structures or dictions can in newspaper story and on television determine or affect audience emotions. The thematic structure also relate to the frequency of the news coverage on a particular story (this means developing story); extent of interest given to the news, repetition of the same story along with videos, and the numbers of reporters and correspondents used on the same story from the media house, and various experts invited to talk about the story.
-------------------	---

Source: Akpoghiran, I. Patrick (2022).

Fig.2: Another Framing Process: A Simple Process of How News Frames Influenced Audience Emotions

Reporter/Editor	News Presentation	Audience Emotions
<p>Building and Setting of Frame Stage: Reporter and editor build and set frame by gatekeeping selection process through writing style, grammatical structures or dictions, filing news story and framing the headline. The agenda setting postulation takes effect here. The editorial policies and the reporter and editor perceptions also take effect here.</p>	<p>The Presentation Stage: News presentation with videos and other supporting elements for TV for example are very persuasive and convincing. Also, the frequency of the story as the story developed, and the duration of the coverage, expert opinions on the issue, and other elements is a second process of how audience are influenced by news frames.</p>	<p>Emotional Stage: Audience reacts and interprets news as presented. Here, audience views or opinions form their emotions on the issue. Audience interpretation and evaluation of the news stem from the two processes. Audience’s influenced on news frames is determined by the two processes. When news issues are identified and discussed by way of pondering about it, analyzing and interpreting it, becomes effect.</p>

Source: Akpoghiran, I. Patrick (2022).

Submission

Having discussed the concept of news frames and how news audience emotions are influenced by news frames, the following points were submitted, that:

- i. News frame is the presentation of the news media aimed at keeping the audience ‘stay tuned’.
- ii. News frame is a process, and all the elements involved in the processes are capable of influencing audience’s emotions.
- iii. News frame is the strong and continuous emphasized on news by which audience emotions are influenced.
- iv. Audience degree of influence to news frame largely depends on the state of the audience’s selection, perception and interpretation processes of the news.

CONCLUSION

News frame is the construct and presentation of the news media. It is news emphasis. News frame is a process with various news elements capable of influencing audience emotions. Individual’s perception and reaction to news is a product of the journalistic news frame. This is because news frames involves selecting and emphasizing words, expressions, and images (for television), and these are capable of influencing audience’s cognitive, attitude and emotional effects. Based on the psychological dispositions to the information processes of selecting and interpreting of news, individual’s perception of and react to news is formed. Individual audience is influenced by what the news media present as news. However, audience emotions to news are limited by the state of mood and degree of selection, interpretations and perceptions.

REFERENCES

Akpoghiran, I.P. (2022). Public Health Risk: Public Views on Panic Reporting and Media Framing of the Covid 19 Pandemic. *New Media and Mass Communication*. Vol.100. DOI: 10.7176NMMC
 Amodu, L.C. (2006). Perception: A determinant for effective communication. *SOPHIA: An African Journal of Philosophy*. 9 (1); 148-153

- Arowolo, S.O. (2017). Understanding framing theory. ResearchGate publication
- Batelaan, N.M; Seldenrijk, A; Bot, M, Balkom, A.J.L.M; Penninx, B.W.J.H. (2016). Anxiety and new onset of cardiovascular disease: critical review and meta-analysis. *Br J Psychiatry*. 208:223-231.
- Beckett, C. (2008). *SuperMedia: Saving journalism so it can save the world*. Chichester, UK: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Beckett, C. (2010). *The value of networked journalism*. London, England: POLIS, London School of Economics and Political Science.
- Beckett, C. & Deuze, M. (2016). *On the Role of Emotion in the Future of Journalism*. Journal of Social Media and Social. 1-6 SAGE publication
- Brüggemann, M. (2014). Between frame setting and frame sending: How journalists contribute to news frames. *Communication Theory*, 24(1), 61– 82.
- Cappella, J. N., & Jamieson, K. H. (1997). *Spiral of cynicism: The press and the public good*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Chong, D., & Druckman, J. N. (2007a). A theory of framing and opinion formation in competitive elite environments. *Journal of Communication*, 57, 99– 118.
- Chong, D., & Druckman, J. N. (2007). Framing theory. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 10, 103–126.
- D'Angelo, P. (2002). News framing as a multi- paradigmatic research program: A response to Entman. *Journal of Communication*, 52, 870– 888
- De Vreese, C. H. (2005). News framing: Theory and typology. *Information Design Journal + Document Design*, 13(1), 51– 62
- De Vreese C.H (2012). New avenues for framing research. *Am Behav Sci* 56: 365–375. doi:10.1177/0002764211426331
- De Vreese, C. H., Boomgaarden, H. G., & Semetko, H. A. (2011). (In)direct framing effects: the effects of news media framing on public support for Turkish membership in the European Union. *Communication Research*, 38(2), 179–205.
- Démuth, A. (2013). Perception Theories. *Edícia kognitívne štúdia*, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/>
- Dong, M & Zheng, J. (2020). Letter to the editor: Headline stress disorder caused by Netnews during the outbreak of COVID-19. Wiley publication. DOI: 10.1111/hex.13055.
- Dorfman, L & Krasnow, I.D. (2013). Public health and media advocacy. *Annual Review of Public Health* publication. 35, 293–306. www.annualreviews.org Retrieved 7th April, 2022
- Dorfman, L & Krasnow, I.D. (2014). Public health and media advocacy. *Annual Review of Public Health* publication. 35, 293–306. www.annualreviews.org. Retrieved 7th April, 2022.
- Entman, R. B. (1993). Framing: Toward clarification of a fractured paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43, 51– 58.
- Fiske, S. T & Taylor, S.E.(1991). *Social cognition* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill
- Gamson, W. A., & Modigliani, A. (1989). Media discourse and public opinion on nuclear power: A constructionist approach. *American Journal of Sociology*, 95,1–37.
- Gerbner, G., & Gross, L. (1976). Living with television: The violence profile. *Journal of Communication*, 26(2), 182–190. doi: 10.1111/j.1460-2466.1976.tb01397.
- Gitlin, T. (1980). *The whole world is watching: Mass media in the making and unmaking of the new left*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Goffman, E. (1974). *Frame analysis*. New York: Free Press.
- Gross, K., & D'Ambrosio, L. (2004). Framing emotional response. *Political Psychology*, 25(1), 1–29.
- Gross, K., & Brewer, P. R. (2007). Sore losers: news frames, policy debates, and emotions. *Harvard International Journal of Press/Politics*, 12(1), 122–133.
- Gross, K. (2008). Framing persuasive appeals: Episodic and thematic framing, emotional response, and policy opinion. *Pol Psychol* 29: 169–192. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9221.2008.00622
- Hänggli, R. (2012). Key factors in frame building: How strategic political actors shape news media coverage. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 56(3), 300– 317.
- Igartua, J.J; Moral-Toranzo, F. & Fernández, I. (2011). Cognitive, attitudinal, and emotional effects of news Frame and group cues, on processing news about Immigration *Journal of Media Psychology*; Vol. 23(4):174–185. DOI: 10.1027/1864-1105/a000050 Hogrefe Publishing.
- Kim, H. J & Cameron, G.T. (2011). Emotions Matter in Crisis: The Role of Anger and Sadness in the Publics' Response to Crisis News Framing and Corporate Crisis Response. *Communication Research* 38(6) 826 –855. Sage publication.

- Lakoff, G. (1996). *Moral politics: What conservatives know that liberals don't*. USA: Chicago University Press.
- Lecheler, S., & de Vreese, C. H. (2013). What a difference a day makes? The effects of repetitive and competitive news framing over time. *Communication Research*, 40(2), 147–175.
- Lecheler, S. & De Vreese, C.H. (2019). *News framing effect*. New York; US, Routledge:.
- Lecheler, S. (2020). The emotional turn in journalism needs to be about audience perceptions/*Digital Journalism*. 8 (2), 287-291.
- Lecheler S.K, de Vreese C.H, Slothuus R (2009) Issue importance as a moderator of framing effects. *Commun Res* 36: 400–425. doi:10.1177/0093650209333028.
- Lecheler, S., Schuck, A. R. T., & de Vreese, C. H. (2013). Dealing with feeling: Positive and negative discrete emotions as mediators of news framing effects. *Communications: The European Journal of Communication*, 38, 189–209. 2013-0011 <https://doi.org/10.1515/commun->
- Liu M.Y; Li NA, Li WA; Khan, H. (2017). Association between psychosocial stress and hypertension: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neurol Res*. 2017;39:573-580.
- López WL, Sabucedo JM (2007). Culture of peace and mass media. *Eur Psychol* 12: 147–155. doi:10.1027/1016-9040.12.2.147.
- Makata, E. C. (2021). *Framing a pandemic: Evaluating Nigerian print media reportage of China before and following the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic*. Being a Master Project Thesis. Saint John's University, Jamaica New York.
- Nabi, R. L. (2002). Anger, fear, uncertainty, and attitudes: A test of the cognitive-functional model. *Communication Monographs*, 69, 204-216.
- Nabi, R. L. (2003). Exploring the framing effects of emotion: Do discrete emotions differentially influence information accessibility, information seeking, and policy preference? *Communication Research*, 30, 224-247.
- Nelson, T. E., & Willey, E. A. (2001). Issue frames that strike a value balance: A political psychology perspective. In S. D. Reese, O. H. Gandy, & A. E. Grant (Eds.), *Framing public life: Perspectives on media and our understanding of social world* (pp. 245– 266). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates
- Neuman W.R, Just M.R, Crigler A.N (1992). *Common knowledge : News and the construction of political meaning*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Otieno, C; Spade, H; & Renki, A. (2013). Effects of news frames on perceived risk, emotions, and learning. *PLOS ONE* 8(11): e79696. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0079696
- Pan, Z., & Kosicki, G. M. (1993). Framing analysis: An approach to news discourse. *Political Communication*, 10, 55-75.
- Pantti, M. (2010). The Value of Emotion: An Examination of Television Journalists' Notions on Emotionality. *European Journal of Communication*, 25(2), 168–181.
- Perrealt, Jr. E. & McCarthy, J. *Basic Marketing: (2005). A Global Managerial Approach*. New York: McGrawHill Companies Inc.
- Petty RE, Cacioppo JT, Schumann D (1983) Central and peripheral routes to advertising effectiveness: The moderating role of involvement. *J Consum Res* 10: 135. doi:10.1086/208954.
- Price, V., Tewksbury, D., & Powers, E. (1997). Switching trains of thought. *Communication Research*, 24(5), 481–506. doi:10.1177/ 009365097024005002
- Scheufele, D. (1999). Framing as a theory of media effects. *Journal of Communication*, 49(1), 103–122.
- Scheufele, D. (2000). Agenda-setting, priming and framing revisited: Another look at cognitive effects of political communication. *Mass Communication and Society*, 3(2–3), 297–316.
- Scheufele, B. (2004). Framing- effects approach: A theoretical and methodological critique. *Communications*, 29(4), 401– 428.
- Scheufele, D. A., & Tewksbury, D. (2007). Framing, agenda setting and priming: the evolution of three media effects models. *Journal of Communication*, 57(1), 9–20.
- Scheufele D.A. & Iyengar S (2012). The state of framing research: A call for new directions. In: Kenski K, Jamieson KH. *The Oxford Handbook of Political Communication*. New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Schmitz, M. F., Filippone, P., & Edelman, E. M. (2003). Social Representations of Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder, 1988–1997. *Culture & Psychology*, 9(4), 383–406. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1354067X0394004>
- Schuck, A. R. T., & Feinholdt, A. (2015). News framing effects and emotions. In R. A. Scott, & S. M. Kosslyn (Eds.), *Emerging trends in the social and behavioral sciences: An interdisciplinary*, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1-9
- Scott, M. D. & Brydon, S.R. (1997). *Dimensions of Communication: An Introduction*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Inc

- Semetko H, Valkenburg P (2000). Framing European politics: A content analysis of press and television news. *J Commun* 50: 93–109. doi:10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.
- Shrum, L.J. (2017). Cultivation Theory: Effects and Underlying Processes. *The International Encyclopedia of Media Effects*. [https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314395025DOI: 10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0040](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314395025DOI:10.1002/9781118783764.wbieme0040)
- Tankard J.W. (2001). The empirical approach to the study of media framing. In: Gandy OH, Grant AE, Reese SD. *Framing public life perspectives on media and our understanding of the social world*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates; pp. 95–106.
- Valenzuela, S; Piña, M; & Ramírez, J. (2017). Behavioral effects of framing on social media users: How conflict, economic, human interest, and morality frames drive news sharing. *Journal of Communication*. doi:10.1111/jcom.12325
- Van Gorp B, Vettehen PH, Beentjes JWJ (2009). Challenging the frame in the news. *Media Psychol* 21: 161–170. doi:10.1027/1864-1105.21.4.161.
- Vliegthart, R., & Roggeband, C. (2007). Framing Immigration and Integration: Relationships between Press and Parliament in the Netherlands. *International Communication Gazette*, 69(3), 295–319. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748048507076582>
- Wahl-Jorgensen, K. (2016). Emotion and Journalism. In T. Witschge (Ed.). *The SAGE Handbook of Digital Journalism* (pp. 128–143). London: SAGE
- Zhang, L. (2015). Publics' emotional responses expressed in different clusters of corporate crises Master thesis in Journalism and Mass Communication, Iowa State University